

1 **Oncogenic KRAS^{G12D} Transfer from Platelet-Like Particles**
2 **Enhances Proliferation and Survival in Non-Small Cell Lung**
3 **Cancer Cells**

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40 **ABSTRACT**

41 In the tumor context, platelets play a significant role in both primary tumor
42 progression, dissemination and metastasis. Analysis of this interaction in various
43 cancers, such as non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), demonstrate that platelets
44 can both transfer and receive biomolecules (e. g. RNA and proteins) to and from
45 the tumor at different stages, becoming tumor-educated platelets.

46 To investigate how platelets are able to transfer oncogenic material, we
47 developed *in vitro* platelet-like particles (PLPs), from differentiated MEG-01 cell
48 line, stably carrying RNA and protein of the KRAS^{G12D} oncogene in fusion with
49 GFP. We cocultured these PLPs with NSCLC H1975 tumor cells to assess their
50 ability to transfer this material.

51 We observed that the generated platelets were capable of stably expressing the
52 oncogene and transferring both its RNA and protein forms to tumor cells using
53 qPCR and imaging techniques. Additionally, we found that coculturing PLPs
54 loaded with GFP-KRAS^{G12D} with tumor cells increased their proliferative capacity
55 at specific PLPs concentrations.

56 In conclusion, our study successfully engineered MEG-01 cell line to produce
57 PLPs carrying oncogenic GFP-KRAS^{G12D} simulating the tumor microenvironment,
58 demonstrating the efficient transfer of this oncogene to tumor cells and its
59 significant impact on enhancing proliferation.

60 **KEYWORDS:** KRAS, Platelet-like-particles, Non-small cell lung cancer, Onco-
61 gene transfer

62 **INTRODUCTION**

63 The intricate interplay between platelets and tumor cells has emerged as a critical
64 factor in cancer development, progression and metastasis. While platelets are
65 traditionally known for their role in hemostasis (1,2), they are increasingly
66 recognized for their multifaceted contributions to tumor biology (3,4). Platelets
67 can act as carriers of tumor-derived proteins, nucleic acids and extracellular
68 vesicles, potentially influencing the tumor microenvironment and accelerating
69 cancer progression (5–7).

70 Recently, increasing attention has been given to the potential role of platelets in
71 transferring both their own cargo and oncogenic material to tumor cells (8,9). This
72 platelet-mediated transfer of oncogenic cargo may contribute to tumor
73 heterogeneity and impacts responses to therapy (10–13). Consequently, platelets
74 can promote tumor cell survival, proliferation, and metastasis through multiple
75 mechanisms, including protecting cancer cells from immune surveillance and
76 facilitating their dissemination in the bloodstream (14,15).

77 Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), which accounts for approximately 85% of
78 all lung cancer cases, remains the leading cause of cancer-related deaths
79 worldwide (16). Despite significant advances in targeted therapies and
80 immunotherapies, the prognosis for patients with advanced NSCLC remains
81 poor, with a 5-year survival rate of less than 20% (17). The molecular complexity
82 of NSCLC, characterized by diverse genomic alterations, presents both
83 challenges and opportunities for therapeutic intervention (18,19).

84 *KRAS* mutations are among the most frequent oncogenic drivers in NSCLC,
85 present in 25-30% of cases (20). These mutations have been shown to drive
86 tumor cell proliferation, survival and metastasis through the activation of various

87 downstream signaling pathways (21,22). In particular, the KRAS G12D variant
88 (KRAS^{G12D}) is highly prevalent and is linked to poor prognosis and resistance to
89 targeted therapies (23). Additionally, studies utilizing platelets as liquid biopsy
90 have demonstrated that mutated *KRAS* variants originating from various tumor
91 types can be transferred to platelets (5,6).

92 Recent advances in understanding the genomic landscape of NSCLC and other
93 cancer types have revealed the complexity of tumor evolution and the
94 development of resistance mechanisms (23,24). The concept of tumor
95 heterogeneity, both spatial and temporal, plays a critical role in shaping treatment
96 strategies and influencing patient outcomes (25). In this context, the potential
97 contribution of platelets to intra-tumoral heterogeneity through the transfer of
98 oncogenic material represents a compelling area of research (9,26). This
99 interaction between platelets and tumor cells could be particularly relevant in the
100 lungs, where recent studies have demonstrated that platelets are produced in
101 significant quantities through immature megakaryocytes residing in the lung,
102 especially in inflammation context (27).

103 In this study we demonstrate the role of oncogenic *KRAS*^{G12D} loaded in platelet
104 like particles (PLPs) generated *in vitro* and its transfer to tumor cells, focusing on
105 its impact on NSCLC progression and survival advantages. We engineered the
106 human megakaryoblastic cell line MEG-01 to express the GFP-KRAS^{G12D} fusion
107 mRNA and protein and examined the production of PLPs carrying this oncogene.
108 Additionally, we investigated the transfer of GFP-KRAS^{G12D} from PLPs to H1975
109 lung adenocarcinoma cells and assessed the functional consequences in terms
110 of cell proliferation.

111 By investigating the mechanisms of platelet-mediated oncogene transfer, our
112 research provides new insights into platelets impact in NSCLC, potentially
113 leading to novel therapeutic strategies.

114

115 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

116 **Cell culture**

117 MEG-01 (RRID:CVCL_0425) and NCI-H1975 (H1975) (RRID:CVCL_1511) lung
118 adenocarcinoma cell lines were obtained from ATCC and cultured in RPMI-1640
119 medium (Biowest, Nuaille, France) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum
120 (FBS, Biowest) and 1X penicillin/streptomycin (PS) (Sigma-Aldrich, Merck, St.
121 Louis, MO, USA). H1975 cells were passed every 5-6 days at a seeding ratio of
122 1:5. MEG-01 cells grow in suspension and were passed weekly at a 1:5 ratio.

123 HEK293T (RRID:CVCL_0063) cells were cultured in DMEM-high glucose
124 medium (Biowest) supplemented with 10% FBS and 1X PS and passed every 3-
125 4 days at a 1:5 to 1:8 ratio using 0.75X TrypLE Express (Thermo Fisher Scientific,
126 Waltham, MA, USA) for 5 min.

127 All cell lines were maintained at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
128 and routinely tested for mycoplasma contamination using the Venor®GeM qEP
129 (Minerva Biolabs, Dublin, Ireland). Cell line authentication was performed using
130 AmpFLSTR Identifiler® Plus (Thermo Fisher Scientific), confirming the cells were
131 mycoplasma-free and STR-validated.

132 **Lentiviral vector constructs**

133 The pRRL-EF1a-PGK-NEO vector, kindly provided by Prof. Trono (EPFL,
134 Lausanne, Switzerland) was used as the control empty vector (EV). The GFP-

135 KRAS^{G12D} cDNA, originally obtained in a pBABE vector from Addgene
136 (Watertown, MA, USA), was sub-cloned into the pRRL-EF1a-PGK-NEO vector
137 using standard molecular techniques.

138 *E. coli* DH5 α were transformed with the final constructs, and plasmid DNA was
139 extracted using NucleoSpin Plasmid kit (Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany).
140 Sequencing of the constructs was performed by StabVida laboratories (Caparica,
141 Portugal). High-concentration plasmids were obtained through maxiprep from
142 transformed *E. coli* DH5 α cells.

143 **Lentiviral vectors production and cell transduction**

144 Lentiviral vectors (LVs) were generated by transfecting HEK293T cells with
145 pRRL-EF1a-PGK-NEO (Control) or pRRL-EF1a-GFP-KRAS^{G12D}-NEO (GFP-
146 KRAS^{G12D}), along with psPax2 (packaging vector) and VSV.G (envelope vector)
147 from Addgene, using the standard calcium-phosphate transfection methods.
148 Supernatants were collected 24 and 48 h post-transfection.

149 Viral titers were determined by serial dilutions of the concentrated LVs on 293T.
150 GFP-positive cells were quantified by flow cytometry 3–5 days post-transduction.

151 Viral supernatants were used for transduction, supplemented with Polybrene
152 Reagent (8 mg/mL, Sigma-Aldrich, Merck). Cells were transduced overnight, and
153 the culture medium was replaced the following morning. Two days post-
154 transduction, cells were selected with G418 (100 mg/mL; Invitrogen, Thermo
155 Fisher Scientific) for 5 days. GFP-positive cells were then sorted using a FACS
156 Aria Fusion (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA).

157 **MEG-01 cell line differentiation and PLP production**

158 The MEG-01 cell line was differentiated with 2 mM valproic acid (VPA) over 12
159 days, a modified protocol from Schweinfurth et al., 2010. On day 0, 1.4×10^6 cells
160 were seeded in a T75 flask containing 14 mL of RPMI medium supplemented with
161 FBS, PS, and 2 mM VPA. The medium was refreshed on day 4 and 8. PLPs and
162 differentiated cells are collected on day 12. To harvest PLPs, the culture
163 supernatant was collected into a 15 mL Falcon tube. and centrifuged at 180xg for
164 5 min to remove cellular debris. Subsequently, the resulting supernatant was
165 filtered through a 5 μ m filter (Merck) and transferred to a low-adhesion 15 mL
166 Falcon tube. This was followed by centrifugation at 1200xg for 10 min. The
167 harvested pellet was washed with PBS, pooled and centrifuged again at 1200xg
168 for 10 min. For co-culture experiments, the final pellet was resuspended in RPMI
169 medium supplemented with FBS and PS.

170 To collect the differentiated cells, the T75 flask was washed with PBS and 0.75X
171 TrypLE was added and incubated for 5 min. Afterward, 1X PBS was added, and
172 cells were gently detached using a cell scraper. The cell suspension was
173 transferred to a 15 mL Falcon tube and centrifuged at 250xg for 5 min to collect
174 the cells.

175 **MEG-01 cell line differentiation for immunofluorescence and confocal**
176 **analysis**

177 Cells were plated at low density in 8-well format (Nalge Nunc International,
178 Naperville, IL, USA), adjusting the density to a final concentration of 1×10^5 cells
179 per well in 200 μ L of medium. Differentiation followed the previously described
180 protocol. On day 12, cells were washed with PBS, fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde
181 (Sigma-Aldrich) in PBS and permeabilized with 0.1% Tween (Sigma-Aldrich) for
182 5 min at room temperature. Blocking was performed with 5% BSA (Sigma-Aldrich)

183 (w/v) in PBS for 30 min with washes carried out in PBS containing 0.1% BSA.
184 Immunostaining was done overnight at 4°C using anti- Hu CD61 (ref. 14-0619-
185 82, Invitrogen) and anti-GFP (ref. 2955S, Abcam, Cambridge; UK) antibodies at
186 final concentration 1:200 diluted in 3% BSA/PBS. After that, samples were
187 washed with PBS containing 0.1% BSA and incubated with secondary antibodies
188 Alexa Fluor 555 Donkey anti-mouse (A31570, Invitrogen) and Alexa Fluor 488
189 Donkey anti-rabbit (A21206, Invitrogen) antibodies diluted in 3% BSA/PBS for 1
190 hour at room temperature. Samples were washed with PBS containing 0.1%
191 BSA. Cells were mounted and counterstained with DAPI using VECTASHIELD®
192 Antifade Mounting Media (Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA).
193 Immunofluorescence images were captured using an Axio Observer Z1 inverted
194 fluorescence microscope (Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany) and processed using ZEN
195 software (Zeiss).

196 **Flow cytometry and ImageStream analysis of MEG-01 cell line**
197 **differentiation**

198 Cells were collected, washed once with PBS and centrifuged at 150xg for 5 min.
199 They were resuspended to a final concentration of 1×10^6 cells/mL in PBS and
200 100 μ L of cells suspension was incubated with anti-human CD61-AF647 antibody
201 (ref. 336408, VI-P12D, Invitrogen) at 1:200 final concentration for 30 min at room
202 temperature. Following incubation, cells were washed with PBS, centrifuged and
203 resuspended in FACS buffer (PBS supplemented with 5% FBS and 2 mM EDTA).
204 Labeled cells were analyzed using either a FACS Canto II flow cytometer or an
205 ImageStream Mark II imaging flow cytometer (Amnis). Data were processed
206 using Cytobank (<https://community.cytobank.org/cytobank/login>) and IDEAS
207 software (Amnis), respectively.

208 Both cells and PLPs were stained as described in the flow cytometry analysis
209 section. After staining, cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 12
210 min and permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich) in PBS for 20 min.
211 Then, cells were incubated with 1 μ M Hoechst (Merck Life Sciences) for 3 min,
212 washed, and resuspended in FACS buffer. Platelets were similarly stained,
213 washed, and resuspended in PBS with 2 mM EDTA. Data were acquired in an
214 ImageStream Mark II imaging flow cytometer and analyzed with IDEAS software.

215 **RNA extraction, RT-PCR, qPCR and Sanger sequencing**

216 Total RNA was extracted using the NucleoSpin® RNA kit (Macherey-Nagel)
217 following manufacturer's instructions. cDNA was synthesized from the extracted
218 RNA using the Transcriptor First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Roche; Basel,
219 Switzerland) following manufacturer's protocol. Gene expression was assessed
220 by qPCR using Brilliant III Ultra-Fast SYBR® Green QPCR Master Mix (Agilent
221 Technologies; Santa Clara, CA, USA) on a 7900HT Fast Real-Time PCR System
222 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Data analysis was performed using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method,
223 with GAPDH as the normalization control. The GFP-KRAS^{G12D} cDNA product
224 obtained from the RT-qPCR was purified and sequenced by StabVida
225 laboratories. qPCR and sequencing primers are listed in Table S1 and Table S2,
226 respectively.

227 **Western blot analysis**

228 For total protein extraction, MEG-01 cells were lysed in RIPA buffer (Sigma-
229 Aldrich) containing protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche) and phosphatase inhibitors
230 cocktail 2 and 3 (Sigma-Aldrich). Cell lysates were separated by molecular weight
231 using SDS-polyacrylamide gels and transferred to cellulose membranes. Proteins
232 were detected using the Odyssey Infrared Imaging System (Li-cor Biosciences;

233 Lincoln, NE, USA). GFP-KRAS^{G12D} was detected with anti-GFP antibody (ref.
234 2955S, Abcam), while α -GAPDH (ref. 60004-1-Ig, Proteintech) was used as a
235 loading control. Western blotting was carried out using standard procedures. All
236 the results showed correspond to the same membrane.

237 **Immunofluorescence and ImageStream of the coculture**

238 Cells were plated at a density of 1×10^5 cells/well and 200 μ L of medium in 8-well
239 format. H1975 cells were co-cultured with either EV or GFP-KRAS^{G12D}-loaded
240 PLPs. After 24 hours, the cells were washed with PBS, fixed in 4%
241 paraformaldehyde (Sigma-Aldrich), permeabilized with 0.2% Triton X-100,
242 blocked with 3% of BSA (Sigma-Aldrich) and stained as previously described in
243 the immunofluorescence and confocal section, with the exception that Cellular
244 Vibrant DiD (V22887, Invitrogen) was added at 10 μ M for staining tumor cells
245 membranes. Immunofluorescence images were acquired using an Axio Observer
246 Z1 inverted fluorescence microscope (Zeiss) and processed with ZEN software.

247 For ImageStream analysis of the coculture, H1975 cells were seeded at a density
248 of 2.5×10^4 cells/well in 24-well plates. Then, cells were cocultured with 25 μ g of
249 either EV or GFP-KRAS^{G12D}-loaded PLPs in 1 mL of medium. After 24 hours the
250 cocultures were harvested, washed with PBS, and centrifuged at 250xg for 5 min.
251 The pellet was resuspended and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 10
252 minutes and permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich) in PBS for 5
253 min. Then, cells were resuspended in PBS to a final concentration of 1×10^6
254 cells/mL. Aliquots of 100 μ L cell suspension were incubated with anti-human
255 CD61-AF647 antibody (Invitrogen) at a 1:200 dilution for 30 min at room
256 temperature. After that, cells were washed twice with PBS, centrifuging at 250xg.
257 Then, cell nuclei were staining with 1 μ M Hoechst (Merck Life Sciences) for 3

258 min, washed, and resuspended in FACS buffer. Data were acquired in an
259 ImageStream Mark II imaging flow cytometer (Amnis, Switzerland) and analyzed
260 with IDEAS software (Amnis).

261 **Functional assay: determination of viability and proliferation of the** 262 **coculture with different amounts of PLPs**

263 H1975 cells were seeded at 5×10^4 cells per well in 96-well plates. After 24 hours,
264 different concentrations of PLPs (0, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 5, 10, 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{well}$) were
265 added. The impact of co-culturing tumor cells with varying amounts of EV or GFP-
266 KRAS^{G12D}-loaded PLPs was evaluated 24 hours post-coculture using WST-1
267 reagent (Roche) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Absorbance at 450
268 nm was measured using a Tecan Infinite 200 Pro microplate reader (Tecan Trader
269 AG, Männedorf, Switzerland). Cell viability was expressed as normalized
270 absorbance relative to control cells.

271 **Statistics**

272 All statistical analyses and graph plotting were conducted using GraphPad Prism
273 (version 8.0 for Windows, GraphPad Software). Expression and functional
274 experiments were performed in both biological and technical triplicates. Data
275 were represented as mean \pm SD or mean \pm SEM. For comparisons between two
276 different groups, a t-test was applied to assess statistical significance. A p-
277 value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

278

279 **RESULTS**

280 **Generation and phenotypic characterization of MEG-01 cell models** 281 **undifferentiated and differentiated and their PLPs**

282 To investigate the potential role of platelets in transferring oncogenic KRAS^{G12D}
283 to tumor cells, we constructed a lentiviral vector containing GFP and KRAS^{G12D}
284 cDNAs fused in-frame linking them with a HA-tag linker, along with a neomycin
285 resistance cassette. We transduced the MEG-01 cell line to express either this
286 GFP-KRAS^{G12D} expressing vector or the EV as a control (Fig. 1A). The
287 differentiation process of MEG-01 cells and subsequent production of PLPs were
288 monitored over a 12-day period (Fig. 1B).

289 Using ImageStream platform, we were able to assess protein expression and
290 localization at a single-cell level. This analysis confirmed the successful
291 expression of GFP-KRAS^{G12D} in MEG-01 transduced cells. Representative
292 images showed the localization and expression levels of Hoechst (nuclear DNA,
293 purple), CD61 (integrin beta 3, red), and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} (green) in both
294 undifferentiated and differentiated MEG-01 cells transduced with the EV or the
295 GFP-KRAS^{G12D} vector (Fig. 1C, D). The platelet surface marker CD61 was
296 consistently localized at the cell periphery in both undifferentiated and
297 differentiated MEG-01 EV and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} cells. In contrast, GFP-KRAS^{G12D}
298 protein was exclusively detected in the MEG-01 GFP-KRAS^{G12D} cell line and was
299 distributed throughout the intracellular region and the perimembrane area (Fig.
300 1C, D, bottom panels). The extended morphology and presence of cellular
301 protrusions in both MEG-01 EV and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} cells further indicated their
302 differentiation status (Fig. 1D).

303 Quantitative assessment of mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) demonstrated a
304 significant increase in CD61 expression upon differentiation in both EV and GFP-
305 KRAS^{G12D} cells. In particular, the MFI of CD61 in differentiated GFP-KRAS^{G12D}
306 cells was 5-fold higher than in undifferentiated cells ($p < 0.001$), reflecting the

307 progression of megakaryocytic maturation. Notably, GFP-KRAS^{G12D} expression
308 was observed exclusively in MEG-01 GFP-KRAS^{G12D} cell line. While this
309 expression persisted throughout the differentiation process, it showed a decline
310 in the differentiated cells (Fig. 1E).

311 PLPs produced from both engineered differentiated cell lines retained the CD61
312 surface marker. Notably, PLPs derived from differentiated MEG-01 GFP-
313 KRAS^{G12D} cells exhibited GFP-KRAS^{G12D} expression, suggesting successful
314 loading of the fusion protein into the PLPs. They also displayed size and
315 morphology consisting of typical platelets, as illustrated in Figure 1F. These
316 results confirm that the engineered MEG-01 cells successfully produce PLPs
317 harboring the fusion protein while retaining key characteristics of native platelets.

318 **Characterization of GFP-KRAS^{G12D}-loaded PLPs**

319 Immunocytofluorescence analysis of differentiated MEG-01 cells revealed
320 proplatelet formation (Fig. 2A, white arrows), a hallmark of platelet production,
321 along with strong CD61 expression in both EV and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} differentiated
322 cells. GFP-KRAS^{G12D} expression was exclusively detected in MEG-01 GFP-
323 KRAS^{G12D} cells (Fig. 2A). Interestingly, GFP-KRAS^{G12D} was also observed within
324 the proplatelets (Fig. 2A, white arrows).

325 To further characterize the molecular profile of the engineered cells and PLPs,
326 we performed quantitative RT-PCR analysis. Platelet-specific genes (*GP9*,
327 *GP2B*) and *KRAS* were expressed in both differentiated cells and PLPs (Fig. 2B).
328 Importantly, the *GFP-KRAS^{G12D}* fusion gene was specifically expressed in the
329 transduced cells and PLPs, with insignificant expression in EV controls (Fig. 2C).
330 Sequence analysis confirmed the presence of the G12D mutation (c.G35A) in the
331 fusion construct at the mRNA level (Fig. 2D).

332 Western blot analysis confirmed the expression of the GFP-KRAS^{G12D} fusion
333 protein expression in both differentiated cells and PLPs GFP-KRAS^{G12D}. A distinct
334 band corresponding to the expected molecular weight of 51 KDa was observed
335 in GFP-KRAS^{G12D} samples, while this band was absent in EV controls, confirming
336 the successful production and incorporation of the fusion protein into PLPs (Fig.
337 2E). GAPDH (37 KDa) was used as the endogenous control. We confirmed that
338 GFP-KRAS^{G12D} expression remained stable in PLPs, making them suitable for
339 co-culture with other cell types to study the transference and impact of this
340 oncogenic protein.

341 **Transfer of GFP-KRAS^{G12D} from loaded PLPs to H1975 tumor cells**

342 To evaluate the potential of PLPs to transfer GFP-KRAS^{G12D} biomolecules in lung
343 tumor context, we conducted co-culture experiments with H1975 lung
344 adenocarcinoma cells. Immunocytofluorescence analysis confirmed the
345 presence of GFP-KRAS^{G12D} within H1975 cells after co-culture with loaded PLPs,
346 indicating successful transfer of the fusion protein (Fig. 3A). Z-Stack analysis
347 further revealed that PLPs were in the same focal plane as the cells, suggesting
348 that PLPs fused with or were internalized by H1975, facilitating the transfer of the
349 GFP-KRAS^{G12D} fusion protein (Fig. 3A, right panel).

350 This observation was corroborated by ImageStream analysis, which
351 demonstrated co-localization of GFP-KRAS^{G12D} and CD61 signals within H1975
352 cells following co-cultured with GFP-KRAS^{G12D}-loaded PLPs (Fig. 3B). In
353 contrast, when H1975 cells were co-cultured with EV PLPs, only the CD61 signal
354 was detected, confirming that GFP-KRAS^{G12D} transfer was specific to PLPs
355 loaded with the fusion protein.

356 RT-qPCR analysis revealed a significant increase in the expression of both total
357 *KRAS* ($p < 0.05$) and *GFP-KRAS^{G12D}* fusion gene ($p < 0.001$) expression in H1975
358 cells following co-culture with GFP-KRAS^{G12D} PLPs, compared to co-culture with
359 EV PLPs (Fig. 3C, D). These results provide compelling evidence for the
360 successful transfer of genetic material from PLPs to tumor cells.

361 **Functional impact of GFP-KRAS^{G12D} transfer on H1975 tumor cell** 362 **proliferation**

363 To investigate the biological significance of the observed PLP fusion and the
364 subsequent effect of the oncoprotein, we evaluated the proliferative capacity of
365 H1975 cells after co-culture with PLPs. Proliferation assays revealed that a 24-
366 hour co-culture with GFP-KRAS^{G12D}-loaded PLPs significantly enhanced H1975
367 cell proliferation compared to EV PLPs co-culture, particularly at lower PLPs
368 concentrations from 0.25 to 5 μg of PLP per well ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4). These results
369 indicate that the transferred oncogenic KRAS^{G12D} retains its pro-proliferative
370 function within recipient tumor cells. However, at higher PLPs concentrations (10
371 to 50 μg of PLP per well), cell proliferation decreased, suggesting potential toxicity
372 at elevated PLP levels (Fig. 4).

373 The co-culture condition using 5 μg of PLPs per well yielded the best results. Both
374 EV and GFP-KRAS^{G12D}-loaded PLPs promoted higher proliferation compared to
375 control without PLPs, with significantly greater proliferation observed in cells
376 exposed to GFP-KRAS^{G12D}-loaded PLPs than those exposed to EV PLPs (Fig.
377 4).

378

379 **DISCUSSION**

380 Our study aimed to investigate the role of platelets in transferring oncogenic
381 *KRAS*^{G12D} to tumor cells and its subsequent impact on NSCLC progression and
382 resistance to therapy. For that purpose, we engineered the MEG-01 cell line to
383 express the GFP-*KRAS*^{G12D} fusion protein and examined the production of PLPs
384 containing this oncogene. Our results confirms that MEG-01 cells were
385 successfully modified to express exogenous proteins, consistent with findings
386 from other studies (29,30).

387 Recent studies demonstrated the role of platelets as carriers of tumor-derived
388 proteins and nucleic acids (6,9,14). This biomolecules transfer can occur within
389 the tumor microenvironment, where platelets are in circulation, or during
390 metastasis, when platelets assist circulating tumor cells in their dissemination
391 (13,31,32). The stable expression of GFP-*KRAS*^{G12D} during the differentiation
392 process, along with its efficient incorporation into PLPs, highlights the potential of
393 these particles as vehicles for transferring oncogenic material to tumor cells
394 (9,33,34).

395 In our study, we demonstrated that the GFP-*KRAS*^{G12D}-loaded PLPs were able
396 to transfer GFP-*KRAS*^{G12D} to H1975 tumor cells. The successful transport of the
397 protein between PLPs and NSCLC was confirmed by immunofluorescence and
398 ImageStream analysis, which showed the presence of GFP-*KRAS*^{G12D} in H1975
399 cells after co-culture with GFP-*KRAS*^{G12D}-loaded PLPs, similar to platelets
400 phagocytosis and protein transfer shown in Martins Castanheira *et al.* (12,24).
401 Additionally, qRT-PCR analysis showed a significant increase in both *KRAS* and
402 *GFP-KRAS*^{G12D} fusion gene expression in H1975 cells post-coculture with GFP-
403 *KRAS*^{G12D} PLPs, validating the transfer of mRNA alongside the protein. As other
404 researchers defend (12,26,35,36), these findings strongly support the hypothesis

405 that platelets can mediate the transfer of oncogenic material (both mRNA and
406 protein) to tumor cells, potentially influencing tumor behavior and progression. In
407 this regard, we offer more information concerning the multifaceted role of platelets
408 in cancer progression (26,32,37) and we extend their function beyond their
409 conventional role in hemostasis (1,2,38).

410 To assess the biological significance of coculture with platelets and the oncogene
411 transfer, we evaluated the proliferative capability of H1975 cells following
412 coculture with PLPs. Proliferation assays revealed a significant increase in H1975
413 cell growth after coculture with GFP-KRAS^{G12D} and EV PLPs with 5 µg of PLPs.
414 Determined PLP concentrations significantly increased the cell growth after
415 coculture with GFP-KRAS^{G12D} PLPs compared to EV PLPs. This suggests that
416 the transferred oncogenic GFP-KRAS^{G12D} maintains its pro-proliferative function
417 within recipient tumor cells, as previously shown (24,34). Furthermore, the
418 enhanced proliferation aligns with the well-established role of mutant KRAS in
419 promoting tumor growth and progression (19). Our findings extend this concept,
420 demonstrating that platelet-mediated transfer of oncogenic KRAS can confer a
421 growth advantage to recipient tumor cells.

422 Our study also underscores the critical need to consider the different cell
423 component of the tumor microenvironment and its interactions with circulating
424 cells, such as platelets, in understanding tumor progression and the development
425 of survival advantages. Another level of complexity is involved in this research,
426 as the implications of our results extends beyond KRAS and NSCLC, suggesting
427 the platelet-mediated oncogene transfer could be a broader phenomenon,
428 potentially relevant to other oncogenes and cancer types. Further studies will be
429 needed to clarify this issue.

430 Our findings emphasize the potential role of platelet-mediated oncogene transfer
431 in promoting tumor progression. Targeting platelets-tumor interactions (21,39,40)
432 or disrupting the transfer of oncogenic material may represent promising
433 approaches to improve treatment outcomes for patients with NSCLC.

434 Taken together, our study provides important insights into the role of platelets in
435 oncogene transfer and tumor progression, but it still raises several questions for
436 future research. First, an interesting issue to fully understand is the exact
437 mechanisms of how platelets, or PLPs as our model, transfer oncogenic material
438 to tumor cells, whether through fusion, endocytosis, or other processes. Future
439 efforts should also assess the clinical relevance of this phenomenon by analyzing
440 both tumor biopsies and circulating platelets from NSCLC patients and tracking
441 oncogenic material during disease progression. That could allow the
442 development of novel liquid biopsy techniques and offer new insights into
443 resistance mechanisms.

444 In conclusion, our study successfully engineered MEG-01 cells to produce PLPs
445 carrying oncogenic KRAS, demonstrating the efficient transfer of this oncogene
446 to tumor cells and its significant impact on enhanced proliferation and drug
447 resistance. These findings provide novel insights into the mechanisms of tumor
448 progression mediated by platelet-tumor cell interactions. By elucidating the role
449 of platelet-mediated oncogene transfer, this research opens avenues for the
450 development of new therapeutic strategies and personalized medicine
451 approaches for NSCLC patients.

452

453 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

454 The authors confirm that all data supporting the results included in this manuscript
455 are available in the article document or in its accompanying supplemental
456 materials.

457

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482

483 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

484 J.C.-H.: designed and performed the investigation, methodology, data curation,
485 formal analysis, analyzed the data, data and figure visualization, and wrote the
486 original draft; G.M.-N., J.M.S.-M. and I.A.-P. methodology and performed the in-
487 vestigation; M.P.M. and A.G.-D.: performed the investigation; J.X.: methodology;
488 S.P.R. and C.T.P.: provided resources, research supervision and visualization;
489 P.J.R and M.J.S.: conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration,
490 research supervision, data and figure visualization, and wrote the original draft.
491 All the authors reviewed the manuscript.

492

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- 616

617 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

618 **Figure 1. Generation and differentiation of MEG-01 cell line expressing the**
619 **fusion protein GFP-KRAS^{G12D}.** **A** Schematic representation of the lentiviral
620 vectors designs: Empty vector and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} vector. LTR: long terminal
621 repeats. EF1 α and mPGK: promoters. **B** Schematic representation of MEG-01
622 cell line differentiation and PLP production on day 12. **C** Representative
623 ImageStream images of undifferentiated MEG-01 EV (top) and GFP-KRAS^{G12D}
624 (bottom) cell lines. Channels indicate the localization and expression levels for
625 Hoechst (nucleic DNA, purple), CD61 (red) and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} (green); the last
626 channel corresponds to the merged channels, except for the brightfield. **D**
627 Representative ImageStream images of differentiated MEG-01 EV (top) and
628 GFP-KRAS^{G12D} (bottom) cell lines. Channels indicate the same as in panel C. **E**
629 Mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) comparison of CD61 (left) and GFP-KRAS^{G12D}
630 (right) in MEG-01 EV and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} non-differentiated and differentiated.
631 Data represent the mean \pm SD for three independent experiments. Statistics were
632 assessed with ANOVA two-way plus Tukey multiple comparison test (Statistically
633 significant differences: ns = non-significant, *p < 0.05, ***p < 0.001). **F**
634 Representative ImageStream images of PLP EV (top) and GFP-KRAS^{G12D}
635 (bottom) produced from MEG-01 on day 12. Channels indicate the same as in
636 panel C.

637 **Figure 2. Production of PLP charged with GFP-KRAS^{G12D} from differentiated**
638 **MEG-01 cell line.** **A** Immunocytofluorescence of differentiated MEG-01 EV (top)
639 and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} (bottom). Channels indicate the localization and expression
640 levels for CD61 (red), GFP-KRAS^{G12D} (green) and DAPI (nucleic DNA, blue); the
641 last channel corresponds to the merged channels. The arrows indicate the

642 proplatelet formation. Scale bar = 10 μ m. **B** qRT-PCR analysis showing the
643 expression of *GP9*, *GP2B* and *KRAS* genes in differentiated MEG-01 EV and
644 GFP-KRAS^{G12D} and PLP produced at day 12. **C** qRT-PCR analysis showing the
645 expression of the fusion gene in differentiated MEG-01 EV and GFP-KRAS^{G12D}
646 and PLP produced at day 12. **D** Characterization of fusion gene cDNA coding
647 sequence (mutation corresponds to c.G35A). **E** Western blot analysis detecting
648 the GFP-KRAS^{G12D} fusion protein in both MEG-01 differentiated and PLP.
649 GAPDH is used as a loading control. Molecular weights: GFP-KRAS^{G12D} (51 kDa)
650 and GAPDH (37 kDa). Data in plots represent mean \pm SD for three independent
651 experiments. Statistics was assessed with two-tailed unpaired Student's t-test
652 (Statistically significant differences: ***p < 0.001).

653 **Figure 3. PLP fusion and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} transfer to H1975 tumor cells. A**
654 Immunocytofluorescence of H1975 cells coculture with PLP EV (top) and GFP-
655 KRAS^{G12D} (bottom). Channels indicate the localization and expression levels for
656 DiD (gray), CD61 (red), GFP-KRAS^{G12D} (green), DAPI (nucleic DNA, blue) and
657 merge channel. The last image corresponds to ortho Z-stack slide. Scale bar =
658 10 μ m. **B** Representative ImageStream images of coculture of H1975 cells with
659 PLP EV (top) and GFP-KRAS^{G12D} (bottom). Channels indicate the localization
660 and expression levels for Hoechst (nucleic DNA, purple), CD61 (red) and GFP-
661 KRAS^{G12D} (green); the last channel corresponds to the merged channels, except
662 for the brightfield (BF). **C** qRT-PCR analysis showing the expression of *KRAS*
663 gene in coculture of H1975 cells with PLP EV and GFP-KRAS^{G12D}. **D** qRT-PCR
664 analysis showing the expression of the fusion gene in coculture of H1975 cells
665 with PLP EV and GFP-KRAS^{G12D}. Data in plots represent the mean \pm SD for three

666 independent experiments. Statistics was assessed with Two-tailed unpaired
667 Student's t-test (Statistically significant differences: *p < 0.05).

668 **Figure 4. Evaluation of the effect in proliferation of PLP GFP-KRAS^{G12D} in**
669 **H1975 tumor cells.** Proliferation assay of H1975 cells coculture with different
670 concentrations of PLP EV and PLP GFP-KRAS^{G12D}. Data in plots represent the
671 mean ± SEM for three independent experiments. Statistics was assessed with
672 Two-tailed unpaired Student's t-test (Statistically significant differences: ns = non-
673 significant, *p < 0.05).